

CLINICAL-NEUROLOGICAL FEATURES OF STRABISMUS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article examines the influence of neurological clinical-functional characteristics in children with the consequences of perinatal damage to the nervous system (PDDNS) and impairment of the oculomotor apparatus on the choice of treatment tactics for strabismus.*

Keywords: *disorder, disease, congenital, PDDNS, acquired.*

Strabismus (heterotropia, squint) is a defect in binocular vision. Treatment of the disease involves both pediatric ophthalmologists and neurologists. In normal eye positioning (orthophoria), the eye muscles move synchronously, and the visual axes of both eyes remain parallel. They align with the middle of the eye slit and the retina. This ensures that visual images coincide and are processed by the analyzer into a single image, thus achieving binocular vision. In strabismus, the eye muscles do not work in harmony, which is visually noticeable through asynchronous movement of the iris. The images that the brain receives from the eyes do not match. The nervous system is unable to combine them into a single image. The central part of the visual analyzer, in order to protect itself, blocks the image from the deviating eye. Gradually, the visual function of the affected eye diminishes. Oculomotor disorders rank second in the structure of eye pathology in children, accounting for 2-6% of total eye pathology, with 60-80% of cases requiring surgical treatment. It has been established that the pathological changes in the oculomotor apparatus (OMA) observed in children (strabismus, movement restriction, nystagmus) are predominantly of a paretic nature and are consequences of perinatal damage to the nervous system of ischemic-hypoxic origin. Intracranial hypertension, cervical birth trauma, which often leads to ischemia in the nuclei of the oculomotor nerves (OMN), their degenerative changes, and, as a result, a deficiency in the function of the nuclear apparatus, the III, IV, and VI nerve trunks, their internuclear connections, forming part of the medial longitudinal fasciculus, can disrupt the function of neuromuscular synapses and the extraocular eye muscles. The regulatory mechanisms of the eye muscle apparatus are organized on multiple levels. Motor defects, when any of the oculomotor muscles (OMM) are impaired, are topically specific, which corresponds to the relatively constant innervation zones.

In recent decades, strabologists have focused on developing new methods of specialized ophthalmological treatment for strabismus (pleoptics, orthoptics, diploptics, chemodenervation, and surgical correction). However, as practice has shown, the success of the treatment depends not only on the condition of the visual apparatus but also on the functional state of the brain, which regulates the central control of eye movements.

For the timely and accurate diagnosis of oculomotor disorders in children, it is necessary to search for markers of not only structural-morphological but also functional deficiencies in the nervous system, even in subclinical manifestations, while assessing the impact of the brain's

regulatory systems on the formation and activity of the oculomotor apparatus and its adaptive and compensatory capabilities.

Objective: To study the influence of neurological clinical-functional characteristics in children with the consequences of perinatal nervous system damage (PDDNS) and oculomotor apparatus dysfunction on the choice of treatment tactics for strabismus.

Material and Methods. The work is based on the results of comprehensive clinical-neurological, ophthalmological, and neurophysiological examinations and treatment of 222 children aged 1 month to 15 years. The children were divided into two groups: the main group — 150 children (90 boys (60.0%) and 60 girls (40.0%)) with dysfunctions of the extraocular muscles (EOM) presenting strabismus, and the control group — 72 children without EOM dysfunction (32 boys (44.44%) and 40 girls (55.56%)). The average age in the main group was 5.7 years, and in the control group, it was 6.2 years.

According to the type of oculomotor apparatus (OMA) damage, the patients in the main group were distributed as follows: 114 patients had damage to the abducens nerve (partial — 98 children, complete — 16 children), of which 4 children had bilateral damage, combined with paresis or paralysis of the oculomotor nerve and/or trochlear nerve — 52 children, trochlear nerve — 36 children (partial — 24 cases, complete — 12 children), 6 of them had bilateral damage, oculomotor nerve — 32 children (partial — 28 children, complete — 4 children), convergence paresis or paralysis was noted in 10 children, and nystagmus was observed in 6 patients.

The patients were also classified based on the time of onset of strabismus: congenital — 30 children, from 6 months to 1 year — 54 children, from 1 year to 3 years — 20 children, older than 3 years — 46 children.

According to the study protocol, all children underwent the following diagnostic methods: clinical-anamnestic, clinical-neurological, and ophthalmological examinations, neurophysiological techniques, including electroencephalography (EEG), ultrasound Doppler of head and neck vessels, reoencephalography, Stange test, and omegametry. Along with traditional methods, the method of superpositional electromagnetic scanning (SEMS) of the brain, visual apparatus, and cervical spine was included, allowing not only the study of brain structures but also the oculomotor muscles (EOM). Based on indications, computerized tomography or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain and cervical spine was also performed.

The type and volume of surgical treatment depended on the degree of deviation (determined by compensatory testing), the remaining strength of the affected muscle (4 degrees of hypofunction), the degree of hyperfunction of the contralateral synergist and ipsilateral antagonist (4 degrees of hyperfunction), and clinical data were compared with SEMS findings of the EOM, as well as the size of the eyeball.

Thus, the most frequent clinical manifestation of the energy-deficient condition of the brain (hypoergosis) is the cerebrastrhenic syndrome as a basic foundation for delayed manifestations of perinatal cerebral disorders, including those affecting the function of the ocular motor apparatus (OMA).

Analysis of the EEG data of the examined children revealed significant changes in the bioelectrical activity of the cerebral cortex (BA), the appearance of dysfunction in brainstem structures, and paroxysmal activity during functional tests (photostimulation, hyperventilation), as well as insufficient recovery of BA levels after functional tests.

The decrease in the functional state of the midbrain stem structures and the appearance of widespread paroxysmal activity indirectly indicated chronic brain hypoxia, which serves as the physiological basis for functional insufficiency of the central regulatory system, including the OMA. Recovery of the baseline BA level after functional tests (compensation) was insufficient in the children of the main group and significantly reduced in 70 children (46.7%), confirming brain hypoergosis.

Analysis of hemodynamic indicators from ultrasound Doppler of cerebral vessels and rheoencephalography (REG) showed a deficiency in cerebral blood circulation in the vertebrobasilar basin, with REG data indicating $14.27 \pm 1.59\%$.

The graph shows that REG and ultrasound Doppler data of the cerebral vessels during functional tests (head turns to the sides) are significantly correlated ($r=0.69$).

The inadequacy of the baseline cerebral blood flow combined with the depletion of compensatory mechanisms of the CNS creates conditions for the reduced functional state of brainstem structures responsible for eye movement regulation.

Analysis of the Stange test results revealed significant changes in the stability of children with PPNNS and ocular motor disorders to transient hypoxia compared to the control group ($P<0.01$). Children with PPNNS showed reduced stability to transient hypoxia in the Stange test, with a reduced apneic threshold (PAT) averaging 24 seconds. This indicates depletion of central and peripheral mechanisms for regulating oxygen-dependent systems for energy supply in the child's body (hypoergosis).

In our study, omega-potential was recorded in children once during "operational rest" as an integrated indicator of the child's systemic age-related activity.

As seen in Table 3, a marked decrease in omega-potential to 17.69 ± 0.37 mV was noted in children of the main group. In the control group, the omega-potential was 37.11 ± 1.6 mV ($P<0.01$), which corresponds to an optimal level of wakefulness.

Statistical analysis of the neurophysiological examination data of children in the main group revealed a decrease in background bioelectrical activity (BA) (according to EEG data), the Stange test, and omega potential ($P<0.001$). The results of Superpositional Electromagnetic Scanning (SEMS) of the brain revealed low neuronal activity in 72.0% of cases (54 children) and dystrophic changes in the white matter of the cerebral cortex in 94.7% of cases (71 children) in children with eye movement disorders (GDN).

In the main group of children, changes in SEMS data of the brain were observed. The primary role in the pathogenesis of these clinical manifestations is attributed to dystrophic changes in the brainstem and periventricular tissues around the anterior and posterior horns of the lateral ventricles in the brain tissue.

SEMS of eye movement muscles (GDM) in children with strabismus revealed signs of dystonia in all cases, corresponding to the clinical picture of paresis or paralysis. Our clinical evaluation and statistical analysis of GDM activity amplitude using the SEMS method showed that ideal muscle balance corresponds to a functional activity value of GDM in the range of 30-34 relative units. In the group of patients with strabismus, activity values of GDM less than 30 relative units indicated hypofunction (paresis or paralysis), while values above 34 relative units indicated hyperfunction. There was a significant difference in the amplitudes of bio-potentials between the muscles of synergists and antagonists.

Thus, the results of the comprehensive examination allowed us to identify insufficiency in the central regulatory mechanisms of GDM function in children with clinical signs of GDM dysfunction due to perinatal hypoxic-ischemic brain damage. We assessed their functional status, based on which a program for stagewise pleoptic, orthoptic, and surgical treatment of strabismus in children was developed. Ophthalmological treatment was carried out concurrently with neurological treatment. As a result of surgical correction of strabismus, all operated patients showed a statistically significant reduction in the angle of deviation of the eyeball ($P < 0.01$).

Follow-up examination of all operated patients after 1 year and a majority of patients after 3 years allowed for a comparative analysis of the dynamics of immediate and long-term results of surgical treatment. This analysis showed a significant reduction in residual deviation in all patients who underwent surgical treatment.

Conclusions

1. Long-term consequences of perinatal CNS damage in children with eye movement dysfunction, manifesting as paralytic (paretic) strabismus, are caused by brain hypoxia, leading to a decrease in neurometabolism, the development of chronic oxygen-dependent hypoperformance (hypoergosis), and central regulatory mechanism insufficiency.
2. Immaturity of the regulatory systems, with existing deficiencies in cerebral blood flow, particularly in the vertebrobasilar system (VBB) due to natal cerebrospinal trauma, results in functional insufficiency of the child's visual-nerve apparatus, often manifesting clinically as eye movement disorders, such as strabismus.
3. Early diagnosis of central regulatory mechanism dysfunctions in children allows for the prevention of focal neurological consequences of perinatal CNS damage and the implementation of etiopathogenetic treatment.
4. Surgical treatment planning for strabismus should take into account the child's neurological status and the degree of dysfunction of the eye movement muscles, which improves its effectiveness.

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